

BIODEGRADABLE POLYETHYLENE FILM BASED RECYCLING OF CORNSTARCH**Anindita Bhattacharya¹ and Alka Tangri²**¹Department of Chemistry, Christ Church College, Kanpur²Department of Chemistry, Brahmanand Degree College, Kanpur**ABSTRACT**

It is the “throwing away” tendency of humans and the long life of polymers which are responsible for environmental pollution. Recycling of polymers has become a common feature nowadays. There is a need for further improvement/modification of this conventional and simple recycling process because of its inherent problems such as identification, separation, compatibility, etc. Incineration and chemical recycling are other options available to processor/consumer. Problems of environmental pollution necessitate the development of biodegradable and water-soluble polymers.

INTRODUCTION

Polymers are the materials of today’s choice because of their excellent properties like light weight, high strength/weight ratio, easier processing, low cost, abundant availability of raw materials, corrosion resistant, good insulation, etc. Polymers are used in a variety of fields ranging from domestic to engineering, insulation to conduction, water resistance to water absorption applications and so on. They have further increased the shelf life of food products – a step to help in storage of the cooked products and this is a boon for the working class people. In automobile applications, the fuel efficiency has increased because of light weight and tyre life has increased by consistent development in polymer technology. Yield of crops and agricultural products have increased through the use of polymers by retaining the moisture level in the soil and preventing the bacterial attack etc. Polymers help to save the natural resources by replacing wood etc. Poly vinyl chloride is used as a film for canal lining to prevent seepage of water. These are the few special applications of polymers mentioned here in the life of the human being.

Along with so many advantages, plastics have some adverse effect on environment also. The improper disposal of polythene films pose the biggest threat to environment. The government is restricting its use in many of the states. It is not only blocking our drainage systems but affecting the lives of animals also. Lots of animals are dying by consuming these polythene bags. Recently, 40 kg of polythene was recovered from the stomach of cow in Jaipur ⁽¹⁾. It is the throw away tendency of a man, which is responsible for all these problems. We are very careful in using paper, why not in case of polythene bags? Let us be alert in using these polythene bags and start accumulating to sell them like used newspapers. A step to educate the people for its proper use and disposal is the need of hour rather than cursing the polymer.

Plastic waste is available in the form of films, fibers, toys, domestic containers, industrial items, furniture, etc. in the environment. Plastics are either thermoplastic (reusable) or thermoset (non-reusable) in nature. Thermoplastics along with industrial wastes are being reused mostly. It is the thermoset material along with post-consumer waste, which is of prime importance and is responsible for environmental pollution mainly. Table 1 shows some common applications of plastic waste.

Recycling of plastics is not easy due to the following problems:

- Contamination
- Difficulty in collecting, separating, and identifying the plastics.
- Limited technology available for recycling
- Degradation due to repeated processing
- Low bulk densities of polymers
- Availability in less quantity
- Less economic viability
- Time consuming

Material	Fuel Value (Btu/lb)
Plastics	20,000
Fuel Oil	20,000
Coal	9,600

All these factors make recycling of plastics a tough job. Plastics are not properly identified and its mixture is treated more often to mold/fabricate a product, which results in lowering the mechanical properties, mainly because of poor compatibility of polymers. Hence, there is a need for modifying/developing alternative applications of plastic waste. Some of the options available are chemical recycling and incineration. Recycling of biodegradable polymers has started recently.

CHEMICAL RECYCLING

This is the breakdown of polymer waste into usable fractions for reincarnating as polymers, monomers, fuels or chemicals. It includes pyrolysis, gasification, hydrogenation, solvolysis and depolymerization.

Pyrolysis: It is thermal decomposition of plastic wastes at high temperature in absence of oxygen. This process gives wide variety of gases, liquids and solid products depending on the raw material, process and reaction conditions. Major advantages with this process are: ^[2]

- Reduction in volume of waste by over 90%
- No air pollution

Polymer	Waste	Recycled products
PET	Beverage containers	Fibers, fiberfill
HDPE	Containers	Containers
LDPE	Pallet wrap	Reuse bags
	Agricultural fills	
PP	Battery Cases	Vehicle parts, pipes
PS	Coat hangers	Plant pots
	Vending cups	
PVC	Containers	Pipes
Mixed	Mixed	Wood substitute

Gasification: This process converts plastic waste into synthetic or water gas by oxidizing with air or oxygen. Gasification temperature is 1300C to 1500C. Synthetic gas is made up of H₂, CO₂, CO and H₂O. These gases can be used for production of methanol/ammonia or can be used as a reducing agent for steel production in blast furnace process.

Hydrogenation: In hydrogenation, polymer chains are broken into liquid fuels/oils by supply of heat. Quantity of gas and coke produced is almost negligible here. Liquid fuel can be used in refineries or in chemical plants directly or as a substitute for oil.

Solvolysis: Polyurethane, polyester, polycarbonate, polyamide can be split back into their starting chemicals or intermediate products at elevated temperature by hydrolysis, glycolysis, etc. Recycling of polyethylene terephthalate is very common by this process.

De-polymerization: Depolymerization or unzipping is one of the methods to yield monomers by carrying out the reaction at higher temperature. Energy required for depolymerization is higher than polymerization. Poly (methyl metha acrylate) when heated at 400-500°C, it gives methyl metha acrylate monomer. Purity of this monomer is as high as 98% by this technique.

Incineration: It is one of the methods of recycling of plastic waste to produce energy. Both thermoplastics and thermosets can be used here. It is estimated that by burning one ton of plastic, 250 liter of heating oil can be saved ^[3]. A comparison of fuel value of plastics with fuel oil and coal is given in Table 2. Table 3 shows the

energy equivalent and enthalpy of some common plastics. Major drawback with this method is that it gives undesired emission like HCl, SO₂, dioxin, etc.

Plastic	Energy Equivalent (MJ/Kg)	Combustion Enthalpy (MJ/Kg)
PE	69-72	43
PP	73	44
PS (clear)	80	40
PS (high impact)	81	40
ABS	84	87
PVC	53	18
Nylon 6/6-6	154-156	29
PET	84	31
PC	107	29

At present it is the most advanced waste energy utilization technology. We are far behind in this technology as compared to the other countries since all the high calorific value products are removed from the waste before they reach the incinerator. Energy can be recovered in the form of hot water or electricity.

Incineration carried out in rotary kiln is controlled by metering the waste to its combustion chamber and then by controlling the volume of air over and under the burning bed through its grate. Temperature is controlled to prevent the failure of materials of construction. Temperature control is done by varying the amount of air, which may be in 80-100% excess over stoichiometric requirement, by cooling the gases or walls through water pipes and monitoring of the input waste. Temperature is kept above 750 °C for proper combustion and below 1000 °C to prevent ash from melting and clogging the grate or shortening life of refractory materials of construction.

Prime function of incinerator is to destroy the waste as much as possible, to give harmless products, and to avoid the formation of new hazardous organic materials. Its important parameters are temperature, time, turbulence and availability of oxygen. Higher the temperature, at which waste is treated, higher is the chances of destruction of waste completely and less is the probability of unburnt waste or traces of organic byproduct formation. Longer time of treatment of waste at higher temperature enhances the degree of destruction and reduces traces of organic compound being formed. Turbulence is related to the degree of mixing between waste and oxygen in the combustion air and absence of temperature gradient within furnace. Higher is the turbulence, better is the control and access to air which leads to complete destruction of waste. Quantity of air present should not only be sufficient but well over stoichiometric requirement to ensure proper oxidation at all the time. Therefore, the conditions for optimum incineration are high temperature, sufficient residence time in the incineration, high turbulence and excess of air^[4].

CONCLUSION

Besides recycling and land filling of plastic waste, incineration and chemical recycling are other alternative methods of using plastics waste. Chemical recycling give valuable products, which are useful in various chemical industries, whereas incineration can give sufficient energy to meet the thermal and electrical energy requirements. Plastics have high calorific values comparable to oils. Additions of starch in biodegradable polyethylene film needs careful control of melt temperature and addition of CaO as a scavenger to remove the moisture in the films to overcome the fish-eye problems.

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